

Program for the CHANGE workshop

June 18-20, 2024

Program overview

The program is designed to collect data that will allow identification of system-level factors affecting the use of NAMs, including unexpected or hard to observe factors, in a bottom-up, three-step process. The factors could be barriers or enablers.

The first step in the workshop will be to identify anecdotes, the second step will be to identify the anecdotes the participants would like to discuss more, and the third step includes collection of more details about the anecdotes and linking the anecdotes to underlying system-factors.

Day 1	Create long-list of anecdotes (guidance themes one and two).	Step 1
Day 2	Keynote presentation for inspiration.	
	Create long-list of anecdotes (guidance themes three and four).	Step 1
	Create short-list of prioritised anecdotes.	Step 2
Day 3	Build up details of the prioritised anecdotes to get insight into the views from participants in different parts of the regulatory toxicology system.	Step 3
	Map prioritised anecdotes on underlying system-level factors.	
	Summary, next steps, and closing of workshop.	

Detailed program, day 1

Time (CEST)	Activity
12.00-13.00	Registration and lunch
13.00-13.30	Welcome <i>Harald Gjein</i> <i>Sebastian Hoffmann</i> Information <i>Project team</i>
13.30-13.45	Introduction of guidance theme "Prediction versus protection". <i>Arianna Giusti, Cosmetics Europe.</i>
13.45-14.45	Small group discussions. Free-form storytelling and brainstorming of anecdotes. Create a mind map for each anecdote.
14.45-15.15	Break
15.15-15.30	Introduction of guidance theme "Silos". <i>Denise Bloch, German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR).</i>
15.30-16.30	Small group discussions. Free-form storytelling and brainstorming of anecdotes. Create a mind map for each anecdote.
16.30-17.00	Break
17.00-18.00	Large group discussions (Fishbowl*). Free-form storytelling and brainstorming of anecdotes. Create a mind map for each anecdote.
18.00-18.15	Collect participant thoughts on day 1 and introduce the poster session. <i>Project team</i>
18.15-18.45	Mind map poster session. Participants contribute additional thoughts to the mind maps via post it notes.
19.00	Dinner

Detailed program, day 2

Time (CEST)	Activity
08.45-09.00	Arrival
09.00-09.15	Welcome, summarise day 1 and introduce day 2. <i>Project team</i>
09.15-10.00	Keynote presentation Examining Values to Facilitate the Effective Use of NAMs in Regulatory Toxicology. <i>Kevin Elliott, Michigan State University.</i>
10.00-10.15	Introduction of guidance theme "Regulatory versus academic data". <i>Daniele Wikoff, ToxStrategies.</i>
10.15-11.15	Small group discussions. Free-form storytelling and brainstorming of anecdotes. Create a mind map for each anecdote.
11.15-11.45	Break
11.45-12.00	Introduction of guidance theme "Standard operating procedures". <i>Weihshueh Chiu, Texas A&M University.</i>
12.00-13.00	Small group discussions. Free-form storytelling and brainstorming of anecdotes. Create a mind map for each anecdote.
13.00-14.00	Lunch
14.00-15.00	Large group discussions (Fishbowl*). Free-form storytelling and brainstorming of anecdotes. Create a mind map for each anecdote.
15.00-15.30	Mind map poster session. Participants contribute additional thoughts to the mind maps via post it notes.
15.30-16.00	Break
16.00-16.15	Collect participant thoughts on day 2. Introduction of the prioritisation exercise. <i>Project team</i>
16:15-17.00	Prioritisation exercise. Identify anecdotes participants would like to discuss more.
19:00	Dinner

Detailed program, day 3

Time (CEST)	Activity
08:45-09:00	Arrival
09:00-09:30	Welcome, summarise day 2 and introduce day 3. <i>Project team</i>
09:30-10:45	Small group discussions. Build up details of the prioritised anecdotes to get insight into the views from participants in different parts of the regulatory toxicology system.
10:45-11:15	Break
11:15-12:30	Small group discussions. Map prioritised anecdotes onto underlying system-level factors**.
12:30-13:00	Summary, next steps, and closing of workshop. <i>Project team</i>
13:00-14:00	Lunch

*Instead of a large group having an open discussion, a fishbowl is designed to stimulate in-depth discussion and critical reflection. Fishbowls are useful for ventilating, generating, and sharing ideas through collective cognition and diversity, and to foster dynamic participation.

** The Socio-technical theory will be used as a skeleton for the mapping onto system-level factors: Within a system there are **people** with capabilities, who work towards **goals**, follow **processes**, use **technology**, operate within a physical **infrastructure**, and share certain **cultural** assumptions and norms. Systems mapping helps to understand the individual parts of a system and how they are connected and/or relate to each other. This allows us to understand and develop interventions to change the system in a positive way.